

Highlights

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- Controlled laboratory tests on gravel-rubber mixtures (GRM) having three different percentiles of rubber per weight. 5
- Field tests on the large-scale structure of EuroProteas resting on these three GRM layers to investigate their geotechnical isolation capacity. 6
7
- Increase in rubber content resulted in a reduction of the shear modulus and an increase of the damping ratio. 8
- Findings from the laboratory tests align closely with those obtained from field tests. 9
- A GRM layer with a thickness of 0.50 meters composed of 30% rubber content per weight can effectively isolate the structure from an incoming wave seismic field. 10
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Configuration of a gravel-rubber geotechnical seismic isolation system from laboratory and field tests

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ABSTRACT

We present the outcomes derived from controlled laboratory experiments on utilizing gravel rubber mixtures (GRM) as a geotechnical seismic isolation (GSI) stratum beneath the foundational structure of the EuroProteas prototype. The study encompassed three distinct GRM compositions characterized by varying rubber proportions relative to the total mixture weight (0%, 10%, and 30%) employed as the foundation soil. These GSI-structure systems were subjected to external harmonic forces applied atop the structure of EuroProteas across a broad spectrum of frequencies and force magnitudes. Preceding the commencement of field experiments, resonant column and cyclic triaxial compression assessments were conducted on specimens featuring identical rubber fractions and mean grain size ratios. Our laboratory tests revealed that an increase in rubber content resulted in a reduction of the shear modulus (G_o) and an augmentation of the damping ratio (D_o) while concurrently inducing a more linear character in the G/G_o - $\log\gamma$ - D profiles. The findings derived from the laboratory examinations align closely with those ascertained from field investigations. Specifically, it was confirmed that a GSI layer with a thickness of 0.50 meters, composed of a GRM incorporating 30% rubber content, exhibited a discernible reduction in the overall stiffness of the GSI-structure system, accompanied by a corresponding alteration in its fundamental vibrational frequency. The enhanced damping within the system manifested through observable reductions in acceleration recordings and diminished strain development at the base of the GRM layer with 30% rubber content, encompassing a wide range of frequencies.

1. Introduction

The accumulation and disposal of scrap tires has become a major global environmental problem (Edil and Bosscher, 1994). It is estimated that more than 1.5 billion tires are manufactured each year worldwide, with nearly 24% of them being produced in the European Union (Rowhani and Rainey, 2016; Torretta, Rada, Ragazzi, Trulli, Istrate and Cioca, 2015). Additionally, it is estimated that over 800 million scrap tires are disposed of annually, leading to serious environmental issues. As vehicle demand continues to increase, these numbers are expected to grow in the coming years. Unfortunately, only a few developed countries (such as the USA and Japan) have implemented regulations to manage waste tire recycling and reduce their disposal. On

the other hand, most developing and agricultural countries have yet to explore alternative uses for scrap tires, which are usually thrown away in landfills when they reach the end of their life cycle, creating severe environmental concerns (Tasalloti, Chiaro, Murali and Banasiak, 2021).

Many researchers have explored alternative and sustainable uses of scrap tires in various industrial applications. During the last two decades, recycled rubber grains produced from mechanically shredded scrap tires have attracted significant research interest and have been introduced in civil engineering projects (Edeskär, 2006; Oikonomou and Mavridou, 2009; Tsang and Pitilakis, 2019). Granulated rubber is characterized by low unit weight, high hydraulic conductivity, low bulk density, and high elastic deformability (Edil and Bosscher, 1994; Edeskär, 2006; Anastasiadis, Senetakis and Pitilakis, 2012a; Senetakis, Anastasiadis and Pitilakis, 2012a; Tasalloti et al., 2021), and has already been

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43 included in the ASTM and CEN standards (ASTM-D6270-
44 08, 2008; CEN, 2010).

45 Research has also focused on the use of granulated
46 rubber mixed with granular soils in geostructures. The dy-
47 namic properties of soil rubber mixtures (SRM) and gravel
48 rubber mixtures (GRM) have been extensively studied by
49 many researchers. The experimental study performed by
50 Feng and Sutter (2000) illustrated that the shear modulus
51 of SRM decreases, and the damping ratio of SRM increases
52 with increasing rubber content. In contrast, the mixture with
53 increased rubber content showed a more elastic response due
54 to the elastic nature of rubber. Kim and Santamarina (2008)
55 performed experiments using the bender element method
56 on SRM of particle size ratio $D_{50,r}/D_{50,s} > 1$ (where $D_{50,r}$
57 is the mean grain size of rubber particles and $D_{50,s}$ is the
58 mean grain size of soil particles). In contrast to Feng and
59 Sutter (2000), the reported results showed that the shear
60 wave velocity doesn't decrease monotonically. Still, instead,
61 an increase is observed for rubber content $\leq 20\%$, followed
62 by a decline for increasing rubber content which becomes
63 significant for values above 40%.

64 Over the last decade, the Research Unit of Soil Dy-
65 namics and Geotechnical Earthquake Engineering at the
66 Aristotle University of Thessaloniki in Greece has con-
67 ducted extensive experimental and theoretical research on
68 soil-granulated rubber mixtures. Over 500 experiments, in-
69 cluding resonant column tests, cyclic triaxial compression
70 tests, monotonic triaxial compression tests, and direct shear
71 strain tests, have been performed to evaluate the influence
72 of rubber content on the small-strain and nonlinear dynamic
73 properties of SRM and GRM. Anastasiadis, Senetakis, Piti-
74 lakis, Gargala, Karakasi, Edil and Dean (2012b); Anas-
75 tasiadis et al. (2012a); Senetakis and Anastasiadis (2015)
76 examined the small strain dynamic properties of SRM and

GRM with rubber content of up to 35% of the mixture 77
weight. Based on a series of resonant column tests, they 78
showed that the small strain dynamic stiffness (G_o) de- 79
creases and the initial damping (D_o) rises with increas- 80
ing rubber content due to the increased number of con- 81
tacts between the rubber particles. Similar results were re- 82
ported by Banzibaganye and Vrettos (2022), who performed 83
RC tests on large-diameter SRM specimens composed of 84
different types of sands (uniform and poorly graded) and 85
irregular-size granulated rubber and tire chips. Moreover, 86
Senetakis et al. (2012a), Senetakis, Anastasiadis, Pitilakis, 87
Souli, Edil and Dean (2012b), Nakhaei, Marandi, Sani Ker- 88
mani and Bagheripour (2012), Pistolas (2015) and Pistolas, 89
Anastasiadis and Pitilakis (2018) proposed strain-dependent 90
shear modulus degradation and damping ratio curves derived 91
from cyclic triaxial and resonant column tests over a wide 92
range of strain amplitudes of SRM and GRM specimens of 93
a wide range of rubber content per mixture weight. 94

95 Granulated rubber or tire chips have been studied numer- 96
ically or experimentally as a lightweight backfill material of 97
retaining walls (Youwai and Bergado, 2004; Hazarika, Ko- 98
hama and Sugano, 2008; Tsinaris, Anastasiadis and Pitilakis, 99
2018) and bridge abutments (Argyroudis, Palaiochorinou, 100
Mitoulis and Pitilakis, 2016) or as a drainage layer (Edil 101
and Bosscher, 1994). At the same time, they were also 102
proposed in the design of embankments (Bosscher, Edil and 103
Kuraoka, 1997) and lately as a reinforcement layer to pre- 104
vent liquefaction-induced settlement of structures (Hazarika, 105
Yasuhara, Karmokar and Mitarai, 2007; Terzi, Erenson and 106
Selcuk, 2015; Nikitas and Bhattacharya, 2023).

107 Numerical investigations have demonstrated that SRM 107
or GRM can be employed as a geotechnical seismic isolation 108

(GSI) system in the form of a layer beneath the foundation of a structure (Tsang, 2008; Mavronicola, Komodromos and Charmpis, 2010; Tsang, Lo, Xu and Neaz Sheikh, 2012; Pitilakis, Karapetrou and Tsagdi, 2015; Brunet, de la Llera and Kausel, 2016; Tsang and Pitilakis, 2019; Dhanya, Boominathan and Banerjee, 2020; Pistolas, Pitilakis and Anastasiadis, 2020). Utilizing GRM as an isolation layer has immediate ecological benefits. Additionally, it is considered a cost-effective option for the seismic isolation of traditional buildings in developing countries. The low modulus of the SRM/GRM foundation layer decreases the horizontal and vertical motions of the foundation, as well as the rocking stiffness of the structures (Tsang and Pitilakis, 2019; Pistolas et al., 2020). However, there are only a few experimental studies on using GRM as a GSI system in the literature, and these are mainly limited to laboratory and small-scale testing. Kaneko, Orense, Hyodo and Yoshimoto (2013) conducted a pseudo-dynamic (hybrid) test to investigate the positive effects of SRM in the seismic isolation of structures and to prevent liquefaction. Xiong, Yan and Li (2014) showed that the structural motion of rigid blocks founded on SRM layers is reduced with increasing thickness of the layers. Tsiavos, Alexander, Diambra, Ibraim, Vardanega, Gonzalez-Buelga and Sextos (2019) studied the sliding behavior of structures with SRM layers of varying mean size ratios and thicknesses using shaking table tests. On the other hand, Tsang, Tran, Hung, Pitilakis and Gad (2021) conducted centrifuge experiments, which revealed a decrease in the structural requirements of a model based on SRM.

The first full-scale experimental campaign on the dynamic response of EuroProteas prototype structure founded on GRM layers acting as a GSI system was recently performed (Pitilakis, Anastasiadis, Vratsikidis, Kapouniaris, Massimino, Abate and Corsico, 2021). The results revealed

that a GSI layer with a height of 0.50 m and formed of a GRM with 30% rubber content per weight could effectively isolate the structure. The results of ambient noise measurements and free- and forced-vibration tests showed that the stiffness of the GSI-structure system was significantly reduced, and the damping was increased due to the energy dissipated in the GRM layer. This caused a change in the resonant frequency or period of the soil-GSI-foundation-structure system.

Here, we complement the field test results reported in Pitilakis et al. (2021) with a series of laboratory tests to estimate the strain-dependent dynamic characteristics of the GRM. The field tests are briefly presented, and then we focus on the resonant column and cyclic triaxial compression tests that were carried out in the laboratory on GRM with 0%, 10%, and 30% rubber content to determine the small strain dynamic properties and the shear modulus reduction and material damping curves. A GRM with 30% rubber content shows a rubber-like behavior and higher damping ratio values in high-strain conditions. The laboratory tests further explain the GSI-structure system's dynamic response in the forced vibration experiments. It is demonstrated that when the structure is based on the GRM layer with 30% rubber content, the system's resonant frequency is reduced in comparison to the 0% rubber content values. Moreover, the system's damping is increased due to the increased material damping of the GRM, as indicated by the significantly reduced values of the recorded acceleration at the bottom of the GSI layer. Shear modulus reduction and damping increase curves with shear strain are given for the different GRM configurations.

Figure 1: EuroProteas prototype structure

2. Field Experiments

2.1. Field test Structure

The EuroProteas prototype structure, located at the EuroSeisTest experimental site, was built to serve as a test structure for the exploration of soil-foundation-structure interaction effects and the examination of wave propagation in soil media caused by the vibration of the structure (Figure 1).

Two rectangular concrete slabs, each measuring 3.00 x 3.00 x 0.40 meters, form the top part of the structure. It is supported by four steel columns of SHS 150 x 150 x 10 mm section. To ensure symmetry, X-braces of L 100 x 100 x 10 mm section are connected to the columns on all four sides. The columns are fixed to a reinforced concrete slab identical to the superstructure, which serves as a shallow foundation. The total mass of the structure is approximately 28.5 Mg, and its full height is 5.0 m.

The EuroProteas X-bracing and upper roof slab can be removed, changing the mass and stiffness of the structure and, therefore, its fixed-base frequency. This frequency was numerically calculated to range from 1.78 to 13.06 Hz. In the experiments discussed in this article, the EuroProteas structure was configured with X-bracing on all four sides and two roof slabs, resulting in a fixed-base fundamental

natural frequency of 9.13 Hz. Further information on the design and construction of EuroProteas can be found in Ptilakis, Rovithis, Anastasiadis, Vratsikidis and Manakou (2018), Amendola, Silva, Vratsikidis, Ptilakis, Anastasiadis and Silvestri (2020), and Vratsikidis, Ptilakis, Anastasiadis and Kapouniaris (2022).

2.2. Foundation Soil

The EuroSeisTest test site's soil stratigraphy and its physical and dynamic characteristics have been thoroughly examined and documented in past geophysical and geotechnical studies (Ptilakis, Raptakis, Lontzetidis, Tika-Vassilikou and Jongmans, 1999; Raptakis, Chávez-García, Makra and Ptilakis, 2000; Manakou, Raptakis, Chávez-García, Apostolidis and Ptilakis, 2010). The soil profile immediately below the structure was defined in detail using geotechnical and geophysical surveys carried out prior to construction of the structure, including drilling boreholes, down-hole tests, resonant column, and cyclic triaxial tests on undisturbed soil samples (Ptilakis et al., 2018). The shear wave velocity of the foundation soil varies from 100 to 150 m/s down to a depth of 5m and then increases to over 250 m/s at a depth of 25 m.

In this experimental study, three GRMs with varying rubber fractions and gravel were examined. An excavator was used to dig three 3.2 x 3.2 m square-plan pits to a depth of 0.5 m. The first pit was filled with gravel only, acting as a benchmark GSI case, while the other two were filled with GRMs containing 10% and 30% rubber by weight, respectively. Based on the percentage of the rubber content, the three GSI systems are referred to here as GRM100/0, GRM90/10, and GRM70/30 for the three rubber contents of 0, 10%, and 30%, respectively. We also placed a thin geotextile layer over the base and the sides of the pit to prevent the GSI from mixing with the soil beneath and

Table 1
Physical properties of the GRM used as foundation soil layers.

GRM ID	Rubber content (%)	$D_{50,r}/D_{50,g}$	D_r (%)	γ_d
100/0	0	-	98	16.2
90/10	10	0.16	98	15.2
70/30	30	0.16	59-71	11.8

around it. The physical characteristics of the GRM used in the experiments are outlined in Table 1.

An electric site mixer was used to mix the two materials on-site. A small amount of water (2-3% per mixture) was added during the mixing process to ensure proper contact of the material particles and to prevent possible segregation of the rubber grains during the compaction. The GRM was placed in the pits in two layers of 0.25m each. The bottom layer was compacted for about 10 minutes, and the top layer for 13 minutes using a soil compactor roller. A comprehensive explanation of the installation of the GRM layers on-site is provided in Pitilakis et al. (2021).

2.3. Instrumentation at field

Four triaxial accelerometers were placed on the foundation slab in a cross formation to record the slab's translation, rocking, and any potential out-of-plane motion (Figure 2a). In addition, four accelerometers (Etna2 from Kinemetrics Inc. and CMG-5TCDE from Guralp Systems Ltd.) were placed on the top of the roof slab; two of them were arranged along the axis that was parallel to the direction of the shaking (in-plane) and the other two were located at the opposite corners of the slab to record any out-of-plane motion (Figure 2b).

Furthermore, to monitor the response inside the GSI layer, we buried four uniaxial accelerometers (Kistler Holding AG) inside the GRM layer along the loading axis at three different levels. Figure 2c shows the exact position of the uniaxial accelerometers inside the pit. One was installed

approximately at the top of the GSI layer (0.09 m), two of the uniaxial accelerometers were installed in the middle of the layer (0.25 m), and one at the base of the layer (0.50 m). The uniaxial accelerometers were installed along the axis parallel to the in-plane shaking direction. Before installation, each uniaxial accelerometer was fixed inside a small rectangular waterproof plastic box for protection. Additionally, we attached a 20cm wooden stick to ensure the accelerometer's verticality in every box. Moreover, we protected the cable of the accelerometer by placing it inside a flexible plastic tube. Every accelerometer was placed inside the pit in the pre-designed positions, and subsequently, sand was added to surround the box. After that, material from the GSI layer (i.e., GRM90/10) was added above the sand to protect it from each layer's compaction.

A 1.2-m shape-acceleration array (Measurand, Inc.) equipped with eight triaxial MEM sensors was installed immediately below the foundation's geometrical center. (Figure 2c). The sampling rate of all the instruments was set to 200 Hz. The positive x-axis of the instruments was aligned parallel to the positive x-direction of the structure, which was at an angle of 30° with the magnetic North and coincided with the loading axis. The raw data output was processed following the guidelines in Boore and Bommer (2005) as outlined in Pitilakis et al. (2021).

2.4. Field testing campaign

The experimental campaign comprised ambient noise measurements and free- and forced-vibration tests. All the instruments recorded ambient noise while the structure was placed on top of each GRM layer before the free- and forced-vibration test series were conducted. A comprehensive account of the ambient noise measurements and the free-vibration experiments is provided in Pitilakis et al. (2021).

Figure 2: . A plan view of the instrumentation is shown, including (a) the foundation slab, (b) the roof slab with triaxial accelerometers (the hatched area indicates where the external shaker is positioned), and (c) a cross-section of the structure and the GRM instrumented with the SAAR and uniaxial accelerometers.

291 However, only recordings from the forced-vibration tests
 292 will be utilized in this paper due to their greater amplitude.

293 The MK-500U eccentric mass vibrator system (provided
 294 by ITSAK-EPP0) was installed at the center of the upper
 295 roof slab and used to generate harmonic excitation for the
 296 forced vibration experiments. The vibrator’s eccentricity
 297 could be adjusted between 0.15 and 11.31 kg-m using four
 298 pairs of steel plates (configuration A, B, C, and D) of
 299 different sizes. The output force amplitude was adjusted to
 300 cover a range from 0.07 to 28.50 kN in a frequency range of
 301 1–10 Hz (Table 2). The structure was shaken for 25 seconds
 302 to reach a steady state at each excitation frequency.

Table 2

Summary of the forced-vibration experiments per each foundation soil mixture.

Test ID	Eccentricity (kg-m)	Frequency Range (Hz)	Force Amplitude (kN)
1	1.85	1-10	0.07-7.30
2	3.83	1-10	0.15-15.50
3	6.93	1-10	0.30-27.30
4	11.31	1-8	0.50-28.50

3. Laboratory testing

3.1. Tested Materials

A significant laboratory testing program was conducted at the Research Unit of Soil Dynamics and Geotechnical Earthquake Engineering of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki in Greece to determine the physical, mechanical, and dynamic properties of the three GRM used in the field experiments as foundation soil layers.

Figure 3: Gravels (a) C1D21, (b) C1D9, and rubber (c) R3 and (d) R2 were used in the experiments.

Table 3

Characteristics and classification of the natural and synthetic materials in our tests.

Properties \ Data	Natural Materials		Synthetic Materials	
	Gravel	Gravel	Rubber	Rubber
Material	C1D21	C1D9	R3	R2
Material code	C1D21	C1D9	R3	R2
G_s (gr/cm^3)	2.67	2.67	1.10	1.10
D_{10} (mm)	14.69	6.87	2.07	0.97
D_{30} (mm)	18.80	7.91	2.67	1.27
D_{50} (mm)	20.76	8.96	3.27	1.58
D_{60} (mm)	21.67	9.48	3.56	1.73
C_u	1.48	1.38	1.72	1.79
C_c	1.11	0.96	0.97	0.97
e_{max}	1.385	1.266	1.616	1.465
e_{min}	0.844	0.765	1.075	1.000
Classification	GP	GP	GR	GR

it would be impossible to prepare a remolded sample that
fits the maximum allowed dimensions. To address this issue
and to estimate the small-strain dynamic properties of the
GRM, we prepared an equivalent GRM mixture using gravel
and granulated rubber with smaller medium grain size based
on Anastasiadis et al. (2012b), Senetakis et al. (2012b)
and Pistolas et al. (2018) who reported that GRM with the
same mean grain size ratio ($D_{50,r}/D_{50,g}$) have approximately
the same response in low-strain conditions. Therefore, we
tested an equivalent GRM composed of the materials C1D9
(Figure 3b) and R2 (Figure 3d) to estimate its small-strain
dynamic properties. We tested the C1D9-R2 mixture in the
RC and Cyclic Triaxial Compression (CTRX) apparatuses
to validate the reliability of the results. The quarry gravel
with angular particles C1D9 ($C_u \approx 1$ & $D_{50,g} \approx 9$ mm)
is classified as GP according to ASTM-D2487-17 (2017)
and ASTM-C136M-19 (2019) specification. In contrast, the
R2 ($D_{50,r} \approx 2$ mm) material was constructed using a syn-
thetic-granulated rubber material composed of recycled tire
shreds. Table 3 summarises the properties of the C1D9 and
R2 materials.

The specific gravity, G_s , of gravels C1D21 and C1D9
was found equal to 2.67, while the corresponding value
for the two rubber fractions, R3 and R2, was calculated at

Figure 4: Grain size distribution curves of the gravel and rubber materials used in the experiments

352 1.10 according to the ASTM-D854-02 (2002) specification.
 353 Notably, both gravel materials have almost equal coefficients
 354 of uniformity (C_u) and curvature (C_c). A similar remark is
 355 applicable for the granulated rubber materials. The grain size
 356 distribution of the gravel and rubber materials as specified
 357 by the sieve analysis is presented in Figure 4. Table 3
 358 summarizes all the physical properties and classification
 359 characteristics identified from the laboratory tests.

360 3.2. Sample Preparation

361 Standard specimen preparation and consolidation pro-
 362 cedures were followed during the standard laboratory tests
 363 concerning the soil type and the specimen size (reconstituted
 364 grainy specimen). Each specimen is placed in the appara-
 365 tus by procedures that minimize its disturbance. In cases
 366 where ambient isotropic stresses are applied to a membrane-
 367 enclosed specimen, water or air confining pressure is used
 368 for dry samples.

369 To create uniform samples, gravel was mixed with gran-
 370 ulated rubber chips in three different proportions: 0%, 10%,
 371 and 30% rubber content by weight. The specimens were
 372 then formed into cylindrical metal molds in layers of equal
 373 dry mass to match the relative density of the GRM used
 374 in the field experiments. During the field tests, we placed
 375 cylindrical metal molds of 150 mm diameter inside the pits,

which were also filled with the GRM placed in each pit, 376
 and we calculated the void ratio and the relative density of 377
 each GSI layer. Specifically, GRM100/0, GRM90/10, and 378
 GRM70/30 GSI layers had 98%, 98%, and 59-71% of relative 379
 density, respectively, as shown in Table 1. The difference in 380
 the relative density of the third mixture, which was estimated 381
 to be higher at the bottom layer, is thought to be due to the 382
 inadequate compaction of the foundation soil close to the 383
 mold, even though the same compaction tests and energy 384
 were used. 385

As referred to in the previous section, we decided to con- 386
 struct two types of specimens for the laboratory experiments 387
 by considering the kind of materials, the mean grain size 388
 of the gravels, and the maximum allowed dimensions of the 389
 specimen in the RC apparatus campaign. A large specimen 390
 of the C1D21-R3 mixture of 100 mm diameter and 200 mm 391
 height and a smaller specimen of the C1D9-R2 mixture of 392
 70 mm diameter and 140 mm height were constructed. 393

At first, a certain amount of GRM is weighted, which is 394
 determined by the required void ratio of the specimen. Then, 395
 it is separated into fractions of approximately equal mass. 396
 Large specimens with 200 mm height were constructed in 397
 ten layers, whereas small specimens with 140 mm height 398
 were constructed in seven layers. Every layer had approxi- 399
 mately 2 cm of height. We used two containers with GRM 400
 material of equal mass for each layer. The GRM of each 401
 container was added diametrically opposite to the metal 402
 mold to have, as much as possible, a uniform specimen. 403
 After that, each layer was compacted by a metallic tamper 404
 (different for small and large samples) at about the same 405
 compaction energy per specimen's volume. Specifically, for 406
 large specimens with 200 mm height, the first layer was 407
 compacted with 10 tamps, the second layer with 20 tamps, 408
 the third layer with 30 tamps, and so on. Accordingly, for 409

Table 4
Data of gravel rubber mixtures tested and testing program.

Mixture Group	C1D21-R3	C1D9-R2
Parent gravel	C1D21	C1D9
Parent rubber	R3	R2
Rubber content p.w. (%)	0, 10, 30	0, 10, 30
$D_{50,r} / D_{50,g}$	0.16	0.18
Conditions of saturation	Dry	Dry
Specimens geometry (mm)	100×200	70×140
Mean effective stress σ'_o (kPa)	25 - 200	25 - 200
Range of shear strain γ (%)	$10^{-2} - 10^0$	$10^{-5} - 10^{-2}$
Type of experiment	CTRX	RC

410 small specimens with 140mm height, the first layer was
411 compacted with 5 tamps, the second layer with 10 tamps,
412 the third layer with 15 tamps, and so on.

413 3.3. Laboratory test program

414 Table 4 summarizes the experimental laboratory pro-
415 gram performed on the GRM C1D21-R3 and C1D9-R2,
416 including RC and CTRX test series covering a wide dynamic
417 shear strain range. The applied shear strain range is approx-
418 imately 10^{-5} to $10^{-2}\%$ and 10^{-2} to 1% for RC and CTRX
419 experiments, respectively.

420 The Drnevich longitudinal-torsional Resonant Column
421 device was used for the RC experiments. The experimen-
422 tal procedure was completed according to ASTM-D4015-
423 15 (2015) specifications, ASTM-D2166-16 (2016), ASTM-
424 D2850-15 (2015), and ASTM-D4767-11 (2011) regarding
425 issues related to specimen preparation and control of ambi-
426 ent stress.

427 Low and high amplitude torsional vibration tests were
428 conducted at increasing increments of mean confining pres-
429 sure (σ'_o) from 25 to 200 kPa. Each σ'_o step included three
430 low-amplitude and three high-amplitude measurements. Each
431 torsional amplitude level was applied for approximately
432 10 seconds. After each increase in confining pressure, the
433 specimens were allowed 30 minutes to equilibrate before

the low-amplitude tests were performed. This process was 434
repeated for σ'_o values of 25, 50, 100, and 200 kPa. 435

Cyclic Triaxial Compression tests were conducted in a 436
completely electronically and digitally regulated device. Ac- 437
cording to ASTM-D3999-11 (2011) and ASTM-D5311M- 438
13 (2013) specifications, strain-controlled load is applied in 439
undrained conditions. Seven strain-control tests were carried 440
out for each increasing step of mean confining pressure 25, 441
50, 100, and 200 kPa. As with the RC tests, the specimen 442
was allowed to equilibrate for approximately 30 min after 443
the increase in the confining pressure. The frequency of each 444
cyclic strain loading was set to 0.5 Hz for 10 cycles in each 445
strain-control state. It is also mentioned that the dynamic 446
properties of the mixtures in high-strain conditions were 447
calculated according to Kumar, Krishna and Dey (2017) due 448
to the asymmetrical hysteresis loop of the shear stress versus 449
shear strain cycles. 450

The loading frequency between RC and CTRX exper- 451
iments is different, although it is possible to combine the 452
results for soil-granulated mixtures. (Pistolos et al., 2018). 453
It is observed that the ratio of height to diameter for both 454
small and large specimens is approximately 2.0. The small 455
specimens have a diameter of 70 mm and a height of 140 456
mm, while the large specimens have a diameter of 100 mm 457
and a height of 200 mm. 458

459 3.4. Laboratory test results

Figure 5 shows the effect of mean effective isotropic 460
confining pressure σ'_o and the rubber percentage on the (a) 461
shear modulus, G_o , (b) damping ratio, D_o , and (c) shear 462
wave velocity, V_s in low-amplitude strain for the three GRM. 463
As referred to in the previous section, low-strain values of 464
 G_o , D_o , and V_s were estimated from the equivalent mixture 465
group C1D9-R2 from resonant column tests. These figures 466
illustrate that G_o and V_s values systematically decrease as 467

468 the rubber content increases, whereas the opposite trend is
 469 observed in the D_o values. It is essential to mention that
 470 the shear wave velocity was calculated from the following
 471 equation:

$$G_o = \rho * V_s^2 \quad (1)$$

472 Additionally, we noticed that G_o and V_s values increase
 473 as σ'_o increases. This increase is mainly attributed to the
 474 rise in normal stresses at soil-to-soil and soil-to-rubber in-
 475 terfaces. Moreover, the exact opposite trend is noticed with
 476 the D_o values as σ'_o increases. The reduction in the initial
 477 damping ratio with increasing σ'_o is also due to the effect of
 478 the rise in the normal stresses on the particles of the mixture,
 479 which is a result of the limitation of the grains' movement.
 480 The grains' dislocation and the elastic deformation of the
 481 rubber fraction lead to a reduced displacement of the mix-
 482 ture's particles during the low-amplitude measures, resulting
 483 in lower initial damping ratio values.

484 Figure 6 depicts the G - $\log \gamma$ curves of the GRM100/0,
 485 GRM90/10, and GRM70/30, depending on the mean effec-
 486 tive isotropic confining pressure σ'_o . It is seen that when
 487 the amount of rubber is increased, the shear modulus G
 488 is significantly reduced in all the shear strain amplitudes
 489 that we have shown (from $10^{-5}\%$ to 1%). Considering the
 490 previous remarks reported in Figure 5 and 6, it is also evident
 491 that the increase of the σ'_o increases the shear stiffness of the
 492 mixtures due to the rise of normal stresses at the interfaces
 493 of the particles both in low and high amplitude shear strains.

494 In Figure 7, we plot the G/G_o - $\log \gamma$ curves of the three
 495 GRM configurations in four different mean effective isotropic
 496 confining pressures σ'_o . It is clarified that G/G_o - $\log \gamma$ curves
 497 result from the division of the G - $\log \gamma$ curves (Figure 6)
 498 with the initial shear modulus G_o (Figure 5). It is seen that

499 **Figure 5:** Variation of (a) low-amplitude shear modulus, G_o ,
 500 (b) low-amplitude damping ratio, D_o and (c) low-amplitude
 501 shear wave velocity, V_s , versus isotropic confining pressure, σ'_o .

499 when the rubber content is increased, the G/G_o - $\log \gamma$ curves
 500 become more linear as a result of the mixture exhibiting a
 501 more rubber-like behavior. Figure 7 also presents the D - $\log \gamma$

Figure 6: Variation of shear modulus, G , versus shear strain γ (%), for GRM100/0, GRM90/10 and GRM70/30

In typical soils, the more linear shape of the G/G_o - $\log\gamma$ 508
 curve in the medium to high strains indicates higher damping 509
 ratios. This is similar in the case of soil–rubber mixtures. As 510
 shown in Figure 7, increasing the rubber content leads to 511
 more nonlinear D - $\log\gamma$ curves, indicating a reversing trend 512
 at high strains compared to small strains. 513

In Figures 8 and 9, we compare the measured versus 514
 the estimated normalized shear modulus G/G_o and damping 515
 ratio D (%). The measured values result from the labora- 516
 tory tests, as was previously mentioned. The estimated nor- 517
 malized shear modulus and damping ratio were calculated 518
 according to Pistolas et al. (2018). The variation of G/G_o 519
 with shear strain γ is expressed according to the hyperbolic 520
 model, by Equation 2: 521

$$\frac{G}{G_o} = \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{\gamma}{\gamma_{ref,r}}\right)^{a_r}} \quad (2)$$

The damping ratio D values are estimated according 522
 to the same model described thoroughly in Pistolas et al. 523
 (2018). Specifically, damping ratio values are expressed 524
 based on the Equation 3: 525

$$D = D_o + b * \left(\frac{G}{G_o}\right) * D_{Missing,correct,r} * R_c \quad (3)$$

The proposed model is inspired by Darendeli (2001), and 526
 the rubber inclusion is accounted for through the parameter 527
 R_c . Regarding the G/G_o results, we observe a significant cor- 528
 relation between measured and estimated values in the whole 529
 range of the shear strain conditions. This fact is fundamental 530
 to the reliability of laboratory experiments. Furthermore, the 531
 damping ratio results show a good correlation in low-strain 532
 amplitudes, while an intermediate correlation is noticed in 533
 high-strain amplitudes. 534

Figure 7: Variation of normalized shear modulus, G/G_0 , and damping ratio, D , versus shear strain $\gamma(\%)$, for GRM100/0, GRM90/10 and GRM70/30

4. Performance of GRM in the field

4.1. GRM layer response

The response of the GRM layers is of particular interest in the overall evaluation of the GSI system. We investigated the response of the GSI layers in a wide frequency range

Figure 8: Measured versus estimated normalized shear modulus G/G_0 values of GRM.

Figure 9: Measured versus estimated damping ratio $D(\%)$ values of GRM.

by looking at the recordings from the uniaxial accelerometers placed at three different depths inside the layer in the forced vibration experiments. In Figure 10, We present the maximum acceleration values recorded by the uniaxial accelerometers installed in the GRM layers at 0.09 m, 0.25 m (the middle of the GRM layer), and 0.5 m (the bottom of the GRM layer) below the foundation slab, normalized by the horizontal component of the acceleration recorded at the

Figure 10: The maximum acceleration recorded in the GRM at 0.10 m, 0.25 m, and 0.50 m below the foundation slab normalized by the horizontal acceleration recorded at the top of the foundation slab in the forced vibration test 3 (a-c) and 4 (d-f).

548 top of the foundation slab ($\ddot{u}_{fs}$) in the forced vibration tests
549 3 and 4.

550 When EuroProteas is founded on the gravelly layer, a
551 decrease in the motion recorded at 0.09 m below the founda-
552 tion slab by approximately 40% is noticed compared to the
553 foundation acceleration for excitation frequencies over 4 Hz
554 in both experiments. Additionally, the motion at the bottom
555 of the layer is further reduced by almost 65% over the same
556 frequency range. In the case of the GRM90/10, the decrease
557 of the acceleration amplitude at the bottom of the layer is
558 slightly more significant, indicating the modest yet apparent
559 contribution of the 10% rubber content to the energy dissi-
560 pation. The normalized values observed high for frequencies
561 below 3Hz in both GSI systems were caused by the small
562 motion amplitude recorded by the accelerometers, combined

with the low signal-to-noise ratio of the recordings at those
563 frequencies.

564
565 Regarding the GRM70/30, the measured acceleration at
566 the top of the layer is decreased by approximately 50% in
567 both experiments for excitation frequencies between 2 Hz
568 and 5 Hz. Moreover, the amplitude of the motion recorded at
569 the middle and bottom of the layer is reduced by almost 75%
570 and 90%, respectively, enunciating the increased material
571 damping of the GRM with 30% rubber content. Besides,
572 this decrease between the amplitude of the recording at 0.09
573 m depth and the bottom of the layer is more than twofold,
574 showing the impact of the rubber content in the dissipation
575 of the most considerable portion of the energy transmitted
576 by the foundation within a GRM layer of thickness only 0.50
577 m. Furthermore, the amplitude of the acceleration recorded
578 in the whole excitation frequency range at the bottom of

Figure 11: Maximum amplitude of the strain developed in the GRM at 0.09 m, 0.25 m, and 0.50 m below the foundation slab in the forced vibration tests 3 (a-c) and 4 (d-f).

579 the GRM70/30 layer is almost constant and independent of
 580 the excitation frequency, hence the amplitude of the applied
 581 harmonic force. Considering that seismic waves are trans-
 582 mitted from the ground to the structure, opposite to the path
 583 of the system's excitation in our tests, the latter observation
 584 reinforces the effectiveness of the GRM layer as a means of
 585 GSI.

586 Moreover, we calculated the strains γ_{DB} developed in-
 587 side the GRM layer based on the displacement-based method
 588 to understand the system's response better (Zienkiewicz
 589 and Taylor, 1989; Cook, Malkus, Plesha and Witt, 2002).
 590 According to this method, the strain developed due to a
 591 one-dimensional stress wave traveling between two adjacent
 592 points can be calculated as the ratio of the difference of the
 593 displacement between the two points du over their interme-
 594 diate distance dx , as in Equation 4.

$$\gamma_{DB} = \frac{du}{dx} \quad (4)$$

595 The displacement time series are evaluated after double
 596 integrating the uniaxial accelerometer recordings based on
 597 the guidelines in Boore and Bommer (2005). We calculated
 598 the shear strain based on two points' uniaxial accelerometer
 599 recordings in the forced vibration. The first point is 0.17
 600 m below the foundation at the middle distance between
 601 the instruments placed at depths of 0.09 m and 0.25 m. In
 602 contrast, the second point is at approximately 0.38 m at the
 603 middle distance between the second uniaxial accelerometer
 604 at 0.25 m symmetrically to the geometrical center of the
 605 foundation slab and the accelerometer buried at the bottom
 606 of the GRM layer.

607 The maximum strain per excitation frequency developed
 608 at these two points in the forced-vibration Experiments 3
 609 and 4 when the structure is founded on the three GRM is
 610 presented in Figure 11. Regarding the GRM100/0 and the
 611 GRM90/10, the strain at 0.17 m is significantly affected by
 612 the excitation frequency as indicated by the increase in the
 613 calculated strain, which reaches a maximum value greater
 614 than 10^{-1} %, when the shaker frequency is set close to the
 615 resonant frequency of the GSI-structure system. Further-
 616 more, the strain values are reduced by approximately 50-60%
 617 between the two depths in both systems, strengthening the
 618 argument that the contribution of only 10% of rubber content
 619 is negligible. On the other hand, the strain developed in the
 620 GRM70/30 layer seems to be independent of the excitation
 621 frequency, as demonstrated by the more or less constant
 622 amplitude of the estimated strain at both depths. Besides,
 623 we notice that the strain at a depth of 0.38 m is reduced to
 624 approximately 70% of the value estimated at the upper half
 625 of the GSI layer, indicating the increased damping of the
 626 GRM70/30 layer.

627 Based on the calculated values of strain and the G/G_o -
 628 $\log\gamma$ -D curves presented in Figure 7, we can estimate that
 629 in the upper half of the GRM100/0 layer, the shear modulus
 630 is reduced by more 60% when the system is excited close to
 631 its resonant frequency. In contrast, this reduction is slightly
 632 smaller for the same excitation frequency at a depth of 0.38
 633 m. In addition, the damping ratio is increased to 13% and 9%
 634 at 0.17 m and 0.38 m, respectively. On the other hand, based
 635 on the strain developed in a wide excitation frequency range,
 636 the damping ratio is estimated at approximately 18-20% and
 637 10% in the upper and the lower half of the GRM70/30,
 638 respectively. Provided that the damping of the mixture is
 639 significantly risen and the strain value at the depth of 0.38 m

is low, the shear modulus is reduced by only 40% denoting
 the more linear behavior of the mixture.

5. Conclusions

We conducted the first large-scale experimental cam-
 paign in the EuroProteas prototype structure to assess the
 effectiveness of gravel-rubber mixture (GRM) layers placed
 underneath shallow foundations as a geotechnical seismic
 isolation (GSI) system. This paper focuses on the resonant
 column and cyclic triaxial compression tests performed in
 the laboratory to study and determine the dynamic properties
 of three GRM with 0%, 10%, and 30% rubber content per
 mixture weight. The results of the laboratory experiments
 show that:

1. The shear modulus of a GRM in the small-strain range
 decreases with increasing rubber content while the
 initial damping ratio increases.
2. The normalized shear modulus of the GRM with 30%
 rubber content decreases more linearly with shear
 strain, compared to the gravelly soil (0%).
3. The damping ratio increases more significantly as the
 rubber content of the mixture increases with increas-
 ing shear strain.

Regarding the field testing of the isolation efficiency of
 a GRM layer, we tested three GRM configurations with 0%,
 10%, and 30% rubber content per mixture weight. The soil
 pits beneath the foundation had the same plan dimension
 footprint as the foundation and extended to a depth of 0.50
 m. Our results from the forced vibration tests are reported in
 Pitilakis et al. (2021) and in Vratisikidis and Pitilakis (2023).
 We proved that a soil layer of 0.5 m thickness comprising
 of gravel and 30% rubber per weight can effectively act as a
 geotechnical seismic isolation system.

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References

Amendola, C., Silva, F.D., Vratsikidis, A., Pitilakis, D., Anastasiadis, A., Silvestri, F., 2020. Foundation impedance functions from full-scale soil-structure interaction tests. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering* 141, 106523. doi:10.1016/j.soildyn.2020.106523.

Anastasiadis, A., Senetakis, K., Pitilakis, K., 2012a. Small-Strain Shear Modulus and Damping Ratio of Sand-Rubber and Gravel-Rubber Mixtures. *Geotechnical and Geological Engineering* 30, 363–382. doi:10.1007/s10706-011-9473-2.

Anastasiadis, A., Senetakis, K., Pitilakis, K., Gargala, C., Karakasi, I., Edil, T.B., Dean, S.W., 2012b. Dynamic Behavior of Sand/Rubber Mixtures. Part I: Effect of Rubber Content and Duration of Confinement on Small-Strain Shear Modulus and Damping Ratio. *Journal of ASTM International* 9, 103680. doi:10.1520/JAI103680.

Argyroudis, S., Palaiochorinou, A., Mitoulis, S., Pitilakis, D., 2016. Use of rubberised backfills for improving the seismic response of integral abutment bridges. *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering* 14, 3573–3590. doi:10.1007/s10518-016-0018-1.

ASTM-C136M-19, 2019. Standard Test Method for Sieve Analysis of Fine and Coarse Aggregates. Standard. American Society for Testing and Materials, West Conshohocken, PA.

ASTM-D2166-16, 2016. Standard Test Method for Unconfined Compressive Strength of Cohesive Soil. Standard. American Society for Testing and Materials, West Conshohocken, PA.

ASTM-D2487-17, 2017. Standard Practice for Classification of Soils for Engineering Purposes (Unified Soil Classification System). Standard. American Society for Testing and Materials, West Conshohocken, PA.

ASTM-D2850-15, 2015. Standard Test Method for Unconsolidated-Undrained Triaxial Compression Test on Cohesive Soils. Standard. American Society for Testing and Materials, West Conshohocken, PA.

ASTM-D3999-11, 2011. Standard Test Methods for the Determination of the Modulus and Damping Properties of Soils Using the Cyclic Triaxial Apparatus. Standard. American Society for Testing and Materials, West Conshohocken, PA.

ASTM-D4015-15, 2015. Standard Test Methods for Modulus and Damping of Soils by the Resonant-Column. Standard. American Society for Testing and Materials, West Conshohocken, PA.

ASTM-D4767-11, 2011. Standard Test Method for Consolidated Undrained Triaxial Compression Test for Cohesive Soils. Standard. American Society for Testing and Materials, West Conshohocken, PA.

ASTM-D5311M-13, 2013. Standard Test Method for Load Controlled Cyclic Triaxial Strength of Soil. Standard. American Society for Testing and Materials, West Conshohocken, PA.

ASTM-D6270-08, 2008. Standard Practice for Use of Scrap Tires in Civil Engineering Applications. Standard. American Society for Testing and Materials, West Conshohocken, PA.

ASTM-D854-02, 2002. Standard Test Methods for Specific Gravity of Soil Solids by Water Pycnometer. Standard. American Society for Testing and Materials, West Conshohocken, PA.

Banzibaganye, G., Vrettos, C., 2022. Resonant column tests on mixtures of different sands with coarse tyre rubber chips. *Geotechnical and Geological Engineering*, 1–14doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/s10706-022-02244-0.

Boore, D.M., Bommer, J.J., 2005. Processing of strong-motion accelerograms: needs, options and consequences. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering* 25, 93–115. doi:10.1016/j.soildyn.2004.10.007.

Bosscher, P.J., Edil, T.B., Kuraoka, S., 1997. Design of Highway Embankments Using Tire Chips. *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering* 123, 295–304. doi:10.1061/(ASCE)1090-0241(1997)123:4(295).

Brunet, S., de la Llera, J.C., Kausel, E., 2016. Non-linear modeling of seismic isolation systems made of recycled tire-rubber. *Soil Dynamics*

- 749 and Earthquake Engineering 85, 134–145. doi:10.1016/j.soildyn.2016.
750 03.019.
- 751 CEN, 2010. Materials produced from end of life tyres-Specification of
752 categories based on their dimension(s) and impurities and methods
753 for determining their dimension(s) and impurities. Technical Report.
754 European Committee for Standardization (CEN, Comité Européen de
755 Normalisation).
- 756 Cook, R.D., Malkus, D.S., Plesha, M.E., Witt, R.J.W., 2002. Concept and
757 Applications of Finite Element Analysis. 4th editio ed., John Wiley and
758 Sons, New York.
- 759 Darendeli, M.B., 2001. Development of a new family of normalized
760 modulus reduction and material damping curves. Ph.d. thesis. University
761 of Texas, Austin, USA.
- 762 Dhanya, J., Boominathan, A., Banerjee, S., 2020. Response of low-rise
763 building with geotechnical seismic isolation system. Soil Dynamics
764 and Earthquake Engineering 136, 106187. doi:10.1016/j.soildyn.2020.
765 106187.
- 766 Edeskär, T., 2006. Use of tyre shreds in civil engineering applications:
767 technical and environmental properties. Ph.D. thesis. Lulea University
768 of Technology.
- 769 Edil, T.B., Bosscher, P.J., 1994. Engineering Properties of Tire Chips and
770 Soil Mixtures. Geotechnical Testing Journal 17, 453. doi:10.1520/
771 GTJ10306J.
- 772 Feng, Z.Y., Sutter, K.G., 2000. Dynamic properties of granulated rub-
773 ber/sand mixtures. Geotechnical Testing Journal 23.
- 774 Hazarika, H., Kohama, E., Sugano, T., 2008. Underwater Shake Table Tests
775 on Waterfront Structures Protected with Tire Chips Cushion. Journal
776 of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering 134, 1706–1719.
777 doi:10.1061/(ASCE)1090-0241(2008)134:12(1706).
- 778 Hazarika, H., Yasuhara, K., Karmokar, A., Mitarai, Y., 2007. Shaking table
779 test on liquefaction prevention using tire chips and sand mixture, in:
780 Hazarika and Yasuhara (eds), Proceedings of the international workshop
781 on scrap tire derived geomaterials—opportunities and challenges, Yoko-
782 suka, Japan, pp. 215–222.
- 783 Kaneko, T., Orense, R.P., Hyodo, M., Yoshimoto, N., 2013. Seismic
784 Response Characteristics of Saturated Sand Deposits Mixed with Tire
785 Chips. Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering 139,
786 633–643. doi:10.1061/(ASCE)GT.1943-5606.0000752.
- 787 Kim, H.K., Santamarina, J.C., 2008. Sand–rubber mixtures (large rubber
788 chips). Canadian Geotechnical Journal 45, 1457–1466. doi:10.1139/
789 T08-070.
- Kumar, S.S., Krishna, A.M., Dey, A., 2017. Evaluation of dynamic proper-
790 ties of sandy soil at high cyclic strains. Soil Dynamics and Earthquake
791 Engineering 99, 157–167. doi:10.1016/j.soildyn.2017.05.016. 792
- Manakou, M., Raptakis, D., Chávez-García, F., Apostolidis, P., Pitilakis,
793 K., 2010. 3D soil structure of the Mygdonian basin for site response
794 analysis. Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering 30, 1198–1211.
795 doi:10.1016/j.soildyn.2010.04.027. 796
- Mavronicola, E., Komodromos, P., Charmpis, D., 2010. Numerical Inves-
797 tigation of Potential Usage of Rubber-Soil Mixtures as a Distributed
798 Seismic Isolation Approach, in: Civil-Comp Proceedings, Civil-Comp
799 Press. p. Paper 168. doi:10.4203/ccp.93.168. 800
- Nakhaei, A., Marandi, S., Sani Kermani, S., Bagheripour, M., 2012. Dy-
801 namic properties of granular soils mixed with granulated rubber. Soil
802 Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering 43, 124–132. doi:10.1016/j.
803 soildyn.2012.07.026. 804
- Nikitas, G., Bhattacharya, S., 2023. Experimental study on sand-tire
805 chip mixture foundations acting as a soil liquefaction countermeasure.
806 Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering , 1–27doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/
807 s10518-023-01667-1. 808
- Oikonomou, N., Mavridou, S., 2009. The use of waste tyre rubber in
809 civil engineering works, in: Sustainability of Construction Materials.
810 Elsevier, pp. 213–238. doi:10.1533/9781845695842.213. 811
- Pistolas, G.A., 2015. Experimental and numerical investigation of the
812 implementation of recycled materials mixtures in the foundation of
813 structures for the improvement of seismic behaviour, Phd Dissertation
814 (in Greek). Ph.D. thesis. Department of Civil Engineering, Aristotle
815 University of Thessaloniki. 816
- Pistolas, G.A., Anastasiadis, A., Pitilakis, K., 2018. Dynamic behaviour
817 of granular soil materials mixed with granulated rubber: influence of
818 rubber content and mean grain size ratio on shear modulus and damping
819 ratio for a wide strain range. Innovative Infrastructure Solutions 3, 1–14.
820 doi:10.1007/s41062-018-0156-1. 821
- Pistolas, G.A., Pitilakis, K., Anastasiadis, A., 2020. A numerical investiga-
822 tion on the seismic isolation potential of rubber/soil mixtures. Earth-
823 quake Engineering and Engineering Vibration 19, 683–704. doi:10.
824 1007/s11803-020-0589-3. 825
- Pitilakis, D., Anastasiadis, A., Vratisikidis, A., Kapouniaris, A., Massimino,
826 M.R., Abate, G., Corsico, S., 2021. Large-scale field testing of geotech-
827 nical seismic isolation of structures using gravel-rubber mixtures. Earth-
828 quake Engineering & Structural Dynamics 50, 2712–2731. doi:10.1002/
829 eqe.3468. 830

- 831 Pitilakis, D., Rovithis, E., Anastasiadis, A., Vratsikidis, A., Manakou, M., 872
832 2018. Field evidence of SSI from full-scale structure testing. *Soil* 873
833 *Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering* 112, 89–106. doi:10.1016/j. 874
834 *soildyn.2018.04.024.* 875
- 835 Pitilakis, K., Karapetrou, S., Tsagdi, K., 2015. Numerical investigation of 876
836 the seismic response of RC buildings on soil replaced with rubber–sand 877
837 mixtures. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering* 79, 237–252. 878
838 doi:10.1016/j.soildyn.2015.09.018. 879
- 839 Pitilakis, K., Raptakis, D., Lontzetidis, K., Tika-Vassilikou, T., Jong- 880
840 mans, D., 1999. Geotechnical and Geophysical description of EURO- 881
841 SEISTEST, using Field Laboratory Tests and Moderate Strong Ground 882
842 Motion Recordings. *Journal of Earthquake Engineering* 3, 381–409. 883
843 doi:10.1080/1363246990350352. 884
- 844 Raptakis, D., Chávez-García, F., Makra, K., Pitilakis, K., 2000. Site 885
845 effects at Euroseistest—I. Determination of the valley structure and 886
846 confrontation of observations with 1D analysis. *Soil Dynamics and* 887
847 *Earthquake Engineering* 19, 1–22. doi:10.1016/S0267-7261(99)00025-1. 888
- 848 Rowhani, A., Rainey, T.J., 2016. Scrap tyre management pathways and their 889
849 use as a fuel—a review. *Energies* 9, 888. doi:https://doi.org/10.3390/ 890
850 *en9110888.* 891
- 851 Senetakis, K., Anastasiadis, A., 2015. Effects of state of test sample, 892
852 specimen geometry and sample preparation on dynamic properties of 893
853 rubber–sand mixtures. *Geosynthetics International* 22, 301–310. doi:10. 894
854 *1680/gein.15.00013.* 895
- 855 Senetakis, K., Anastasiadis, A., Pitilakis, K., 2012a. Dynamic properties of 896
856 dry sand/rubber (SRM) and gravel/rubber (GRM) mixtures in a wide 897
857 range of shearing strain amplitudes. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake* 898
858 *Engineering* 33, 38–53. doi:10.1016/j.soildyn.2011.10.003. 899
- 859 Senetakis, K., Anastasiadis, A., Pitilakis, K., Souli, A., Edil, T.B., Dean, 900
860 S.W., 2012b. Dynamic Behavior of Sand/Rubber Mixtures, Part II: Ef- 901
861 fect of Rubber Content on G/GO- γ -DT Curves and Volumetric Thresh- 902
862 old Strain. *Journal of ASTM International* 9, 103711. doi:10.1520/ 903
863 *JAI103711.* 904
- 864 Tasalloti, A., Chiaro, G., Murali, A., Banasiak, L., 2021. Physical and 905
865 Mechanical Properties of Granulated Rubber Mixed with Granular 906
866 Soils—A Literature Review. *Sustainability* 13, 4309. doi:10.3390/ 907
867 *su13084309.* 908
- 868 Terzi, N.U., Erenson, C., Selcuk, M.E., 2015. Geotechnical properties 909
869 of tire-sand mixtures as backfill material for buried pipe installations. 910
870 *Geomech Eng* 9, 447–464. doi:https://doi.org/10.12989/gae.2015.9. 911
871 4.447. 912
- Torretta, V., Rada, E.C., Ragazzi, M., Trulli, E., Istrate, I.A., Cioca, L.I., 872
2015. Treatment and disposal of tyres: Two EU approaches. A review. 873
Waste Management 45, 152–160. doi:10.1016/j.wasman.2015.04.018. 874
- Tsang, H., 2008. Seismic isolation by rubber–soil mixtures for developing 875
countries. *Earthquake Engineering & Structural Dynamics* 37, 283–303. 876
doi:10.1002/eqe.756. 877
- Tsang, H., Lo, S.H., Xu, X., Neaz Sheikh, M., 2012. Seismic isolation 878
for low-to-medium-rise buildings using granulated rubber-soil mixtures: 879
numerical study. *Earthquake Engineering & Structural Dynamics* 41, 880
2009–2024. doi:10.1002/eqe.2171. 881
- Tsang, H., Pitilakis, K., 2019. Mechanism of geotechnical seismic isolation 882
system: Analytical modeling. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineer-* 883
ing 122, 171–184. doi:10.1016/j.soildyn.2019.03.037. 884
- Tsang, H.H., Tran, D.P., Hung, W.Y., Pitilakis, K., Gad, E.F., 2021. Per- 885
formance of geotechnical seismic isolation system using rubber-soil 886
mixtures in centrifuge testing. *Earthquake Engineering & Structural* 887
Dynamics 50, 1271–1289. doi:https://doi.org/10.1002/eqe.3398. 888
- Tsiavos, A., Alexander, N.A., Diambra, A., Ibraim, E., Vardanega, P.J., 889
Gonzalez-Buelga, A., Sextos, A., 2019. A sand-rubber deformable 890
granular layer as a low-cost seismic isolation strategy in developing 891
countries: Experimental investigation. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake* 892
Engineering 125, 105731. doi:10.1016/j.soildyn.2019.105731. 893
- Tsinaris, A., Anastasiadis, A., Pitilakis, K., 2018. Numerical investi- 894
gation of improving the seismic response of retaining structures by 895
using lightweight mixtures as backfill material, in: *Proceedings of the* 896
16th European Conference on Earthquake Engineering, Thessaloniki, 897
Greece, pp. 215–222. 898
- Vratsikidis, A., Pitilakis, D., 2023. Field testing of gravel-rubber mixtures 899
as geotechnical seismic isolation. *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering* 900
21, 3905–3922. doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/s10518-022-01541-6. 901
- Vratsikidis, A., Pitilakis, D., Anastasiadis, A., Kapouniaris, A., 2022. 902
Evidence of soil-structure interaction from modular full-scale field ex- 903
perimental tests. *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering* 20, 3167–3194. 904
doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/s10518-021-01286-8. 905
- Xiong, W., Yan, M.R., Li, Y.Z., 2014. Geotechnical Seismic Isolation 906
System - Further Experimental Study. *Applied Mechanics and Materi-* 907
als 580-583, 1490–1493. doi:10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMM.580-583. 908
1490. 909
- Youwai, S., Bergado, D.T., 2004. Numerical analysis of reinforced wall 910
using rubber tire chips–sand mixtures as backfill material. *Computers* 911
and Geotechnics 31, 103–114. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compgeo. 912

913 2004.01.008.

914 Zienkiewicz, O.C., Taylor, R.L., 1989. The Finite Element Method, Vol

915 1: Basic Formulation and Linear Problems. McGraw Hill International

916 Book Co., London.